

DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S EDUCATION: HISTORY, PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. *In the development of women's education, it is important to pay attention to its history, problems and prospects. This issue served to enrich the content of this article.*

Keywords: *women's education, development of women's education, gender equality, girls' education, education system, women in Islamic countries.*

The problem of the development of women's education.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the role of women in the development of the economy, education, health care and many other areas became as important as the role of men. Ever since women have had the opportunity to receive higher education, they have repeatedly proven that they can not only successfully perform household chores, but also manage, design, and make scientific discoveries on an equal footing with men.

However, it took a long time for women to reach their current status. For example, the history of the development of women's education in Russia, which can be considered the beginning of the XI-XII centuries, includes several important stages and shows how difficult the path to equal rights and opportunities was.

Women's Education is full of complex issues and debates related to girls' and women's education (primary education, secondary education, higher education and health education). is a generic term for This term is sometimes called girls' education. It includes gender equality and educational opportunities. The education of women and girls is important for the eradication of poverty. This topic is also related to the topics of single-sex education and religious education for women, where education is taught along gender lines (women are excluded).

Initially, women's education was mainly based on religious education, and natural sciences were prohibited. Many academic studies show that education, especially for women confined to the household, was considered dangerous and meaningless in Poland.

One of the most important conditions that contributed to the development of women's education was the participation of women in the economic life of the country. The improvement of industrial production, their automation, the decrease in the role of physical labor compared to intellectual labor motivated them to develop in the professional field, improve their skills, and increase their income.

Nevertheless, at the current stage, it can be observed that many achievements of women are not taken into account in some cases. Most leadership and high-paying positions are still held by men, and sometimes they do not take colleagues of the opposite sex seriously. In many companies, when selecting candidates for an interview, preference is often given to men, explaining this choice by the fact that a woman pays more attention to housework.

The number of women who have significant influence in socio-political and scientific fields remains small. Even when making important, strategic decisions, they are overshadowed by their male colleagues of a similar status.

Many girls are interested in science, technology and applied arts from a young age. In modern educational centers, studios, and creative workshops, students are trained in various directions, regardless of their gender, and serve to develop their abilities. This also helps Uzbek women to be at the forefront of society.

Uzbek women continue to participate in social and political life, engage in entrepreneurship, and amaze with their inventions and research, so today the issue of women's education is covered in many mass media and is becoming more and more relevant. To understand this more deeply, it is worth diving into history.

The history of the development of women's education.

Women's education, which arose in a religious environment, became secular over time, supplemented by new disciplines and new important figures. In many countries, the most important stages of the development of women's education have taken place.

It has been proven that improving the education level of girls has a positive effect on their health and economic future, which in turn improves the prospects of the society in which they live. The mortality rate of babies whose mothers have primary education is half of the mortality rate of children whose mothers are illiterate. In the poorest countries of the world, 50 percent of girls did not go to secondary school, and there are many countries where this situation continues to this day. However, several studies show that additional education for girls increases their personal income by 15%. Improving women's education and, at the same time, improving women's earning potential will improve the standard of living of their children, as women spend more of their earnings on their families than men.

Education increases a woman's awareness of her own health, as well as the health of her partner and family. In addition, it reduces cases of early marriage, early childbirth or celibacy at all, not having children, not having an official marriage, and strengthens family relationships. Education also improves women's communication with partners and employers and their level of civic participation.

The education system and school play an important role in determining girls' interest in various subjects, including STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics-Academics) subjects, which leads to quality STEM education. can contribute to women's empowerment by providing greater opportunities to use and benefit from it.

Analysis and research evidence on vocational education and business education for women in low- and middle-income countries show that women's education has a significant positive impact on the socio-economics of a country.

When it comes to academic achievement, according to the FAWE conference, girls educated around the sub-Saharan region do not have deep knowledge in mathematics and science. The tendency of girls to enter the priesthood after finishing school has also been widely studied. Nevertheless, formal education provides many internationally recognized benefits. The Fourth United Nations World Conference on Women adopted resolutions promoting the benefits of women's education in Africa as a whole. These were decisions on improving family health, creating high-paying jobs available to women, and monitoring mother and child development.

In most West African countries in the 1950s and 1960s, despite the fact that women's participation in education decreased, the level of education of women is gradually increasing. However, according to UNESCO statistics, there is still a statistical gender disparity in female enrollment and graduation rates.

Impact on the environment.

In developing countries, educating girls and empowering women in general leads to faster development and lower population growth. This can have a positive impact on environmental problems such as climate change. The Special Research Network estimates that educating girls is the sixth most effective measure against climate change (ahead of solar farms, nuclear power, forestry, and many other actions).

Women and their education in Islamic countries.

In Islam, women played an important role in the establishment of many educational institutions, for example, Fatima al-Fihri founded the Al Karauin Mosque. In later centuries, this mosque was converted into an educational institution and entered the Guinness Book of Records as the oldest and continuously functioning institution.

During the Ayyubid dynasty in the 12th and 13th centuries, 160 mosques (houses of worship) and madrasahs (educational institutions) were established in Damascus, 26 of which were funded by women through waqf (charitable trust or guardianship law).

Although it was unusual for women to participate as students in formal classrooms, it was common for women to attend informal lectures and educational activities in mosques, madrasahs, and other public spaces. Although there were no legal restrictions on women's education, some men such as Muhammad ibn al-Haj (died 1336) disapproved of this practice, and during his time lectures were informally examined. Until the 12th century, women made up one percent of Islamic scholars, and after that, an increase in female scholars was observed. In the 15th century, al-Sakhavi devoted an entire volume of his 12-volume biographical dictionary al-*Ḍaw' al-lāmi* to women scholars and gave information about 1075 of them.

It can be seen from this information that Islam honored and respected women and girls in all ages. It is a religion that not only wants them to have their place in society, but also proves it in practice.

At the end of our speech, we can conclude that it is permissible to say that women's education in the whole world needs constant attention. The reason is that women educate the representatives of the next generation. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to create conditions for women to become educated and intelligent. With this, in the future, we will not fail to educate representatives of the future who have their own independent opinion, a broad outlook and can be progressive in any field.

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